

Reduction of Nitroarenes with Sodium Dithionite

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Manuscript received 25 November 1994, accepted 2 February 1995

Sodium dithionite has been reported in the reduction of a variety of functional groups¹. The nitrogen functions which can be reduced by sodium dithionite are aromatic *N*-oxides², azido³, azo⁴, imine⁵ and oxime⁶. Its applications towards nitro group include the conversion of nitroalkenes to oximes and/or ketones⁷, desulphonation of α -nitrosulphones to nitroalkanes⁸, denitrohydrogenation of α -nitroketones to ketones⁹ and reduction of 4-nitro-2,6-lutidine-1-oxide to 4-amino-2,6-lutidine in low yields with concomitant formation of a substantial amount of sulphanic acid derivative¹⁰. Even reduction of nitro groups to amines has been reported in a few examples¹¹, though in poor yields. In view of the unusual behaviour of sodium dithionite towards nitrocompounds, we decided to investigate the potential of this inexpensive reagent towards reduction of nitroarenes systematically.

We are aware that sodium dithionite can be used in a variety of solvents/cosolvents. We chose *p*-chloronitrobenzene as a model substrate for its reactions with sodium dithionite. Various solvents and reaction conditions were attempted. Though the starting material was observed to have disappeared when the reactions were carried out in DMF-water (1 : 1), dioxane-water (1 : 1) and methanol-water (1 : 1), the amine was obtained in very low yields (~7 to 25%). The reduction in ethyl acetate-water (1 : 1) in presence of tetra-*n*-butylammonium hydrogen sulphate also gave a poor yield of the corresponding amine (~15%). However, aqueous acetonitrile and methanol proved to be the solvents of choice.

Here, we report that various nitroarenes (**1a-j**) can be reduced to the corresponding amines in methanol under reflux or in aqueous acetonitrile at room temperature.

1a ; R = Cl e; R = CH₃
1b ; R = Br f; R = NH₂
1c ; R = I g; R = OH
1d ; R = CN h; R = C₆H₅

All the reductions were done in the presence of sodium bicarbonate (twice the molar equivalents of sodium dithionite) to keep the reaction mixture alkaline. The reduction of *p*-chloronitrobenzene was observed to be much slower in the absence of sodium bicarbonate. The optimum ratio for reduction of nitroarenes has been found to be 1 : 3 : 6 (substrate : Na₂S₂O₄ : NaHCO₃). In some reactions more of sodium dithionite was required for complete reduction (sl. nos. 6-8, 10, 20; Table 1). Sulphonic acid derivatives are believed to be the side-products formed in

TABLE 1—REDUCTION OF NITROARENES WITH SODIUM DITHIONITE IN (i) METHANOL UNDER REFLUX AND (ii) AQUEOUS ACETONITRILE AT AMBIENT TEMPERATURE

Sl no	Substrate	Molar equivalents ^a of Na ₂ S ₂ O ₄	Time ^b (in h)	% Yield ^c (amine)	M p. (°C) Found (lit. ^d)
(i) In methanol :					
1	1a	3	2	42	68 (71)
2	b	3	2	40	58 (66)
3	c	3	3	40	59 (63)
4	d	3	8 ^e	30	75 (83)
5	e	3	1.5	40	44 (45)
6	f	5	8	65	137 (141)
7	g	5	12	55	183 ^f (186 ^f)
8	h	4	7	52	51 (51)
9	i	3	6	40	72 (79)
10	j	5	3	40	50 (50)
(ii) In aqueous acetonitrile :					
11	1a	2	5 min	40	68 (71)
12	b	3	1	39	61 (66)
13	c	3	1	43	58 (63)
14	d	3	2	45	80 (83)
15	e	3	1.5	30	45 (45)
16	f	3	4.5	50	137 (141)
17	g	3	3	60	186 ^f (186 ^f)
18	h	3	4	62	50 (51)
19	i	3	3	47	75 (79)
20	j	5	3	41	50 (50)

^aAll the reactions were done in presence of two molar equivalents of sodium bicarbonate for each mole of sodium dithionite. ^bTime for disappearance of nitroarene. ^cIsolated yield. ^dRef. 12. ^eThe nitroarene disappeared in 1 h but the desired product obtained only after longer refluxing. ^fMelts with decomposition.

these reactions. Lower yields of the amines were obtained when a higher molar ratio of the substrate to sodium dithionite (e.g. 1 : 5) was used. The amines were obtained in lower yields even if the reactions were allowed to continue for long periods of time and tlc showed the presence of a complex mixture. The amines are not believed to have been formed from the corresponding azo compounds as no distinct colour change could be observed during the course of the reactions.

Experimental

Sodium dithionite was estimated by known procedure¹³. Methanol and acetonitrile were distilled before use. Commercial grade nitroarenes **1a-c**, **e-h**, **j** were used after recrystallisation; **1d**, **i** were prepared by known procedures. The melting points were determined on tropical labequip apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu 435 spectrophotometer.

General procedure :

Method A. Reduction in methanol : In a typical procedure, a mixture of *p*-chloronitrobenzene (1 g, 6.3 mmol), methanol (25 ml), sodium dithionite (3.90 g, 19 mmol) and sodium bicarbonate (3.20 g, 38.1 mmol) was refluxed on a heating mantle in a system sealed with a mercury trap. The progress of the reaction was monitored by the disappearance of starting material (tlc using benzene as eluent). The reaction was quenched with water (100 ml) and the product was extracted with ether (3 × 10 ml). The combined extract was dried over anhydrous K₂CO₃, the solvent removed on a rotatory evaporator and the product dried in a vacuum desiccator.

Method B. Reduction in aqueous acetonitrile : In a typical procedure, a mixture of *p*-chloronitrobenzene (1 g, 6.3 mmol) dissolved in acetonitrile (15 ml), sodium dithionite (3.9 g, 19 mmol) and sodium bicarbonate (3.20 g, 38.1 mmol) and water (10 ml) was stirred at room temperature in a system sealed with a mercury trap. The reaction was monitored for the disappearance of the starting material (tlc using benzene as eluent). The reaction was quenched and extracted as in method-A and the product isolated.

The product from **1g** was extracted with ethyl acetate (5 × 10 ml) after adjusting the pH of the solution to ~7 with dilute HCl. The product from **1j** was extracted with ethyl acetate (5 × 10 ml).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.S.) is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

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